

10-11 SINFLARDA STEREOOMETRIYA O`QITISHNING ILMIY VA NAZARIY ASOSLARI

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Annotatsiya.

Geometriya fanini o`qitishning nazariy asoslarini o`rganish ko`zda tutilgan.

To`g`ri chiziq va tekislikning o`zaro vaziyatini ma`lumotlarni to`plash va o`rganish. 10-11 sinflarda geometriya fanini o`qitishda pedagogik texnologiyalardan samarali foydalanishni tashkil etish yo`llarini o`rganish.

Kalit so`zlar: Ko`pyoqlar, Stereometriya, tekislik, parallel, perpendikulyar.

Stereometriya so`zi yunoncha Stereo- "qattiq, fazoviy" va yun. metreo (*metreo*) - "o`lchayman" so`zlaridan olingan so`zdir. Stereometriya Yevklid geometriyasining sohasi bo`lib, unda uch o`lchamli, shakllar o`rganiladi. Stereometriyaning ko`pgina masalalarini yechishdan oldin quyidagi keltirilgan to`g`ri chiziq va tekisliklarni ta`rif va teoremlarini yodda tutish lozim.

1. To`g`ri chiziq va tekislikning parallelligi

α tekislik va unga tegishli bo`lmagan a to`g`ri chiziq birorta ham umumiy nuqtaga ega bo`lmasa, u holda ular parallel deyiladi.

2. To`g`ri chiziq va tekislikning parallelizm alomati. Agar to`g`ri chiziq α tekislikdagi biror a to`g`ri chiziqqa parallel bo`lsa, u holda u shu tekislikka ham paralleldir

3. Tekisliklarni parallelligi

Agar α va β tekisliklar birorta ham umumiy nuqtaga ega bo`lmasa, u holda ular parallel deyiladi.

4. Ikki tekislikning parallelizm alomati: α tekislikda yotgan o`zaro kesishuvchi a va b to`g`ri chiziqlar β tekisligida yotgan c va d to`g`ri chiziq'larga mos ravishda parallel bo`lsa, u holda α va β tekisliklar o`zaro paralleldir.

5. To`g`ri chiziq va tekislikning perpendikulyarligi

Agar tekislikni kesib o`tuvchi to`g`ri chiziq tekislikdagi shu kesishish nuqtasidan o`tuvchi istalgan to`g`ri chiziqqa perpendikulyar bo`lsa, to`g`ri chiziq shu tekislikka perpendikulyar deyiladi.

1. To`g`ri chiziq va tekislikning perpendikulyarlik alomati.

Agar tekislikni kesib o'tuvchi to'g'ri chiziq, tekislikning shu kesishish nuqtasidan o'tuvchi ikki to'g'ri chizig'iga perpendikulyar bo'lsa, u holda tekislikning o'ziga ham perpendikulyar bo'ladi.

7. Tekisliklarning perpendikulyarligi. Kesishuvchi ikkita tekislikning kesishgan to'g'ri chizig'iga perpendikulyar bo'lgan uchinchi tekislik ularni perpendikulyar to'g'ri chiziq bo'yicha kesib o'tsa, bu ikki tekislik perpendikulyar tekisliklar deyiladi.

8. Tekisliklarni perpendikulyarlik alomati. Agar tekislik ikkinchi tekislikka perpendikulyar to'g'ri chiziq orqali o'tsa, u holda ular o'zaro perpendikulyar bo'ladi.

9. Tekislikka tushirilgan perpendikulyar va og'ma. Berilgan nuqtadan berilgan tekislikka tushirilgan perpendikulyar deb, berilgan nuqtani tekislikning nuqtasi bilan tutashtiruvchi va tekislikka perpendikulyar to'g'ri chiziqda yotuvchi kesmaga aytiladi. Nuqtadan tekislikgacha masofa perpendikulyarning uzunligi deyiladi. Berilgan nuqtadan berilgan tekislikka o'tkazilgan og'ma deb berilgan nuqtani tekislikdagi nuqta bilan tutashtiruvchi va tekislikka perpendikulyar bo'lmagan istalgan kesmaga aytiladi. Uch perpendikulyar haqidagi teorema.

10. Ikki yoqli burchak va uni o'lchash. Ikkita yarim tekislikdan va ularni chegaralab turgan umumiy to'g'ri chiziqdan tashkil topgan figura ikki yoqli burchak deyiladi. Yarim tekisliklar ikki yoqli burchakning yoqlari, ularni chegaralovchi to'g'ri chiziq esa ikki yoqli burchakning qirrasiga deyiladi. Ikki yoqli burchakning qirrasiga perpendikulyar tekislik bilan hosil qilingan burchak ikki yoqli burchakning chizikli burchagi deyiladi. Ikki yoqli burchakning o'lchovi uchun unga mos chizikli burchakning o'lchovi qabul qilinadi.

11. Ko'pyoqlar. Ko'pyoqlarga doir masalalarni yechishda asosiy ko'pyoqlar turlari va ularning xossalari bilish talab etiladi.

Sirti chekli miqdordagi yassi ko'pburchakdan iborat jism **ko'pyoq** deyiladi. Ko'pburchaklarning tomonlari ko'pyoqni **qirralari** deyiladi. Ko'pyoqni chegaralovchi ko'pburchaklar **ko'pyoqni** yoqlari deyiladi. **Piramida** deb, uning bitta yog'i ixtiyoriy ko'pburchakdan, qolgan yoqlari umumiy uchga ega bo'lgan uchburchaklardan iborat ko'pyoqqa aytiladi. Ko'pburchak piramidaning **asosi**, qolganlari **yon yoqlari** deyiladi. Barcha yon yoqlarining umumiy uchi piramidani **uchi** deyiladi. Piramidani balandligi deb, piramidaning uchidan asos tekisligiga tushirilgan perpendikulyarga aytiladi.

Muntazam piramida deb asosi muntazam ko'pburchakdan iborat bo'lib, balandligi bu muntazam ko'pburchakni markaziga tushuvchi piramidaga aytiladi. Muntazam piramidaning barcha yon qirralari bir-biriga teng; barcha yon yoqlari teng yonli uchburchaklardir. **Muntazam piramida** yon yog'ining balandligi bu piramidani apofemasi deyiladi. Agar piramidaning asosi n - burchakdan iborat bo'lsa, u holda bunday piramida n - burchakli piramida deyiladi. Uchburchakli piramida tetraedr deyiladi. Agar tetraedrning barcha qirralari teng bo'lsa, bunday tetraedr muntazam tetraedr deyiladi.

Muntazam piramidaning yon sirti quyidagi formula yordamida hisoblanadi: $S_{yon} = P \cdot h$,

bu yerda P - piramida asosining perimetri, h - apofema. Piramidaning hajmi quyidagi formula bo'yicha hisoblanadi:

$$V = S \cdot H,$$

bu yerda S - piramida asosining yuzi; H - piramida balandligi.

Piramidani uning asosiga parallel tekislik bilan kesganda ikkita ko'pyoq hosil bo'ladi. Ulardan biri kesik piramida deb ataladi, ikkinchisi piramida bo'lib, u kesik piramidani to'ldiruvchi deyiladi. Kesik piramidani asoslari o'xshash ko'pburchaklardan, yon yoqlari trapetsiyalardan iborat. Kesik piramidaning balandligi deb, oxirlari asoslarida bo'lgan perpendikulyar kesmasiga aytiladi. Agar kesik piramida muntazam piramidaning qismi bo'lsa, muntazam kesik piramida deyiladi. Muntazam kesik piramidaning yon yoqlari teng yonli trapetsiyalardan iborat. Bu trapetsiyalarning balandligi muntazam kesik piramidaning apofemasi deyiladi. Muntazam kesik piramidaning yon sirti quyidagi formula yordamida hisoblanadi.

$$S_{yon} = (P_1 + P_2) \cdot H,$$

bu yerda P_1P_2 - piramida asoslarining perimetrlari; h - apofema.

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